

PECULIARITIES OF ARABIC-BORROWED WORDS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK TRANSLATIONS (THEIR LEVELS OF ACCEPTANCE IN DICTIONARIES)

Abdullayeva Nigina Abdukadirovna
Teacher of Asia International University
(PhD student) Bukhara, Uzbekistan
E-mail: lucky_happy0607@mail.ru

ABSTRACT. This article is designed to enrich the knowledge of religious supplications both in English and Uzbek for native and non-native speakers. Plus, it assists to put forward the idea of analyzing comparative translations and mostly emphasizes on borrowed English words from Arabic language that are considered to be very necessary words almost for the whole Islamic world across the globe.

Key words: Salah, Dua, Imaan, Sujood, Zuhr, Maghrib, Isha, Dhikr, Wudu.

Introduction. Dunyo aholisi sonining tobora oshib borishi, shulardan o'sishda yetakchilik qilayotgan musulmon aholisining duoga bo'lgan qiziqish, ehtiyojlari ham tobora ortib borishiga asosiy sababdir. Bu esa o'z navbatida hozirgi zamonaviy ingliz tiliga Arab tilidan bevosita va bilvosita kirib kelayotgan diniy terminlar, duolarning o'rganishda ko'plab olimlar o'zlarining hissalarini qo'shgan holatda ingliz tilining kundan-kunga boyitishga asosiy sabab bo'layotgan so'zlarning ro'yxati tuzishga erishmoqdalar.

Objective. Hammamizga ma'lumki dunyo bo'yicha kundan kunga arab tili va undagi duolarning o'rganilishiga oid talablarning oshib borishi, shuningdek insonlarning islomiy duo va undagi jummalarning tushunishga intilishi ushbu maqola yaratilishiga turtki bo'ldi deb hisoblasak to'g'ri bo'lar edi.

Methods. Chog'ishtirma qiyoslash, kuzatuv va boshqalar

Results. Kuzatishlar natijasida, ushbu terminlar ingliz tiliga o'zlashtirma so'zlar ekanligi aniqlandi:

Imaan (faith)-iymon¹

Sujood² (the act of prostration) –sajda

Dua (prayer, supplication)—duo

Salah (daily 5 times prayer)—namoz

Zuhr (prayer after the Fajr and before Asr)-peshin

Maghrib³ (sunset prayer) –shom namozi

How common is the noun *maghrib*?

About **0.01** occurrences per million words in modern written English

1

<https://www.wikihow.com/Sujood#:~:text=Sujood%20is%20the%20act%20of,of%20toes%20touch%20the%20ground>

² [www.Hans Wehr Dictionary of Modern Written Arabic.com](http://www.Hans>Wehr/Dictionary%20of%20Modern%20Written%20Arabic.com)

³ https://www.oed.com/dictionary/maghrib_n?tl=true

Ushbu maqoladan ma'lumki, "Maghrib" so'zi 1820-yildan beri ingliz tili iste'molida bo'lib, yildan-yilga bu so'zning keng ishlatilishiga guvohlik bermoqda *Oxford dictionary* ma'lumoti.⁴

Isha14(night prayer)—xufton namozi

Dhikr(remembrance of Allah) –zikr

Wudu⁵ (the practice of ritual washing before daily prayer)—tahorat va boshqalar

"1. the practice of ritual washing before daily prayer

2. a room designated for ritual washing before daily prayer"⁶

ya'ni bunda 2 ma'no ifodalaniladi :

1-tahorat (ibodatlardan oldin qo'llanilishi uchun)

2- xona (tahoratxona-ibodatlardan oldin poklanish uchun)

Yuqoridagi jadval "Wudu" so'zining ishlatilishi, iste'molda bo'lish yillari hisoblaniladi. Unga ko'ra bu so'z "Collins" lug'atida 1970-yildan beri iste'molda bo'lgani va yillar o'tib iste'moldagi darajasi o'zgarganligining guvohi bo'lgan.

Conclusion. Ushbu maqola ikkala(ham ingliz ham o'zbek) tillaridagi mahalliy va nomahalliy tilda so'zloovchi odamlar uchun diniy duolar bilimni boyitishga mo'ljallangan. Shuningdek, qiyosiy tarjimalarning tahliliy g'oyasini ham ilgari surishda yordam beradi.

1. Kundan-kunga ingliz tilini arab tilidan kirib kelib boyitayotgan so'zlar aksariyat ingliz tili lug'atini boyitishiga hissa qo'shibgina qolmay, ular dunyo bo'yicha kundalik so'zlashuv ehtiyojiga aylanyapti.

2. Tadqiqot BuxDU qiyosiy tilshunoslik va lingvistik tarjimashunoslik 2-kurs magistr talabalari orasida olib borilgan va ushbu so'zlarga bo'lgan ehtiyoj yuqori ekanligi o'z isbotini topgan.

3. Kelgusida ushbu terminlarning davomi yig'ilib, ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi ekvivalentlarijamlansa foydali bo'lar edi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1.Al-Bukhari, M. (2017). Sahih al-Bukhari: The Book of Supplications. Dar-us-Salam Publications.

2.Al-Fahad, A. (2004). Al-Qur'an: A linguistic perspective. International Journal of Arabic Linguistics, 15(3), 5-20.

3.Atai, M. (2012). The Qur'an and its interpretation in modern Islamic scholarship. Oxford University

Press.12<https://www.wikihow.com/Sujood#:~:text=Sujood%20is%20the%20act%20of,of%20toes%20touch%20the%20ground>13https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maghrib_prayer14

⁴ https://www.oed.com/dictionary/maghrib_n?tl=true

⁵ <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/wudu>

⁶ <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/wudu>

- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Isha_prayer
<https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/wudu#:~:text=Definition%20of%20'wudu'&text=1.,ritual%20washing%20before%20daily%20prayer>
4. Abdurrahman, M. (2006). Islamic supplications: Their meaning and significance. Al-Mustafa Press.
 5. Ibn Qudamah, A. (The Book of Du'a (Supplications) (250) Chapter: Issues regarding Supplications, their Virtues and Supplications of the Prophet (pbuh)
 6. Khattab, M. (2015). The clear Quran: A thematic translation. Kazi Publications
 7. <https://www.zakeeyaali.com/blog/duas-of-the-prophets-and-the-pious>
 8. <https://sunnah.com/riyadussalihin/16>
 9. The Clear Quran (Mustafa Khattab)
 10. <https://quranwbw.com/duas>
 11. <https://www.wikihow.com/Sujood#:~:text=Sujood%20is%20the%20act%20of,of%20toes%20touch%20the%20ground>
 12. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maghrib_prayer.
 13. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Isha_prayer.
 14. <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/wudu#:~:text=Definition%20of%20'wudu'&text=1.,ritual%20washing%20before%20daily%20prayer>